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Extreme Poverty In The Context Of Human Rights Law: The Case Of Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The major basis of human rights is the preservation of human dignity. Extreme poverty is an assault on human dignity and a violation of the rights of humans. Extreme poverty is both a cause and consequence of violations of human rights and thus amounts to denial of rights. A great percentage of the persons living in Nigeria are living below the global extreme poverty rate. This research was aimed at appraising the extent extreme poverty in Nigeria has resulted to violations of human rights as a result of defect in state responsibility. Key international human rights instruments incorporated into domestic law are also reviewed. Through doctrinal research methodology, the state obligations to respect, to protect and to fulfil the economic, social, and cultural rights and to meet the core minimum obligations are analyzed. Key issues analyzed are non-justiciability of socio-economic rights and the weak institutional and policy frameworks. The major faulty line on the part of the Nigerian state is its inability to create employment and protect the economic rights of the people. The consequential effects of this violation are extreme poverty, gross increase in criminal activities and insecurity in the country. The research concluded that if the violations persist with the present inflation rate and hardship, the possibility of a revolution might be imminent. It therefore recommended the strengthening of the institutional framework, immediate implementation of the various international and national treaties on economic, social and cultural rights and the removal of economic rights from non-justiciable provisions in the Nigerian constitution.

Keywords: Human Rights, Extreme Poverty, Economic Rights, Nigeria.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Poverty has over the years been seen as a concept of economics, it is only of recent that an understanding of poverty and human rights guaranteed are being linked. Thus remarkably, on the 17th of October 2002, during the celebration of the International day for the Eradication of Poverty, the United Nations Secretary General Kofi Annan for the first time explicitly stated that poverty is a denial of human rights.¹ Extreme poverty is a major challenge confronting humanity in the 21st century. Very many persons live in conditions of severe deprivation lacking access to food, clean water, healthcare, housing, education and basic human dignity, this is despite unprecedented global economic growth and technological advancement.

The Vienna Declaration on Programme of Actions has characterized extreme poverty as a violation of human dignity² but avoided calling it a violation of human rights, arguably because of the reluctance of

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¹Dave et al, Poverty, human rights and access to equity: Reflections from Nigeria <<https://www.internationalscholarsjournals.com/articles/poverty-human-rights-and-access-to-equity-reflections-from-nigeria.pdf>> Accessed 6 October 2025

². VDPA, adopted by the World Conference on Human Rights on 25 June 1993 (UN DOC: A/CONF.157/23).

governments to accept legal responsibility.³ It observes that the “existence of widespread extreme poverty inhibits the full and effective enjoyment of human rights”.⁴

Most publications of scholars on the case of extreme poverty in Nigeria reflects more on the inability of poor persons to exercise their human rights based on financial incapability to access justice in Nigeria. Dave et al referred to the denial of the right of fair hearing to poor persons living in Nigeria as a result of inability to pay for legal services.⁵ Eva Brems and Charles O Adekoya⁶ shared same view that poverty leads to denial of the right to fair hearing in Nigeria.

There are generally limited legal publications on poverty as human rights violation in Nigeria. This article will fill this gap in knowledge by critically examining and analysing extreme poverty in Nigeria as a denial and violation of human rights and will proffer answers to the following questions:

- i. To what extent does extreme poverty in Nigeria constitute a violation of human rights under international and domestic law?
- ii. How has Nigeria fulfilled or failed its human rights obligations in addressing extreme poverty?
- iii. What legal and policy reforms are necessary to combat extreme poverty as a human rights concern in Nigeria?

2.1 Human Rights

Human Rights are rights inherent to all human beings, regardless of race, sex, nationality, ethnicity, language, religion, or any other status. Human rights include the right to life and liberty, freedom from torture and slavery, freedom of opinion and expression, the right to work and education, and many more. Human rights are universal and inalienable.⁷ They are generally interrelated, interdependent and indivisible.

Human rights stand above the ordinary laws of the land and are antecedent to the political party itself.⁸ Human rights are seen as cherished entitlements endowed upon every person by virtue only of being a human and which are not extinguishable as they carry the status of innateness, being inherent, inalienable and therefore immutable.⁹ One core foundation of human rights is that all are inherent to human dignity. Hence all human rights have equal status and cannot be ranked in a hierarchical order.¹⁰

Violations of human rights endues at fault line,¹¹ a state of vulnerability. Vulnerability theory provides a template with which to refocus critical attention, raising new questions and challenging established assumptions about individual and state responsibility and the role of law, as well as creating space to address social relationships of inevitable inequality.¹²

2.2 Poverty

Poverty has over the years been seen as a concept of economics, it is only of recent that an understanding of poverty and human rights guaranteed are being linked. Thus remarkably, on the 17th of October 2002, during the celebration of the International day for the Eradication of Poverty, the United Nations Secretary General Kofi Annan for the first time explicitly stated that poverty is a denial of human rights.¹³

³ALSTON, 2005, p. 787.

⁴UN DOC A/CONF.157/24, 1993, cited in Alston, 2005, p. 786.

⁵(n)1.

⁶ Human Rights Enforcement by People Living in Poverty: Access to Justice in Nigeria, Research Gate October 2010 Journal of African Law 54(2):258-282.

⁷Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR), G. A. Res, 217 (111) (A). pmb1, U.N. Doc. A/RES/217 (111) (A) (Dec, 12 1948) recognizing the “inalienable rights of all members of the human family.

⁸⁸Kayode Eso JSC *RansomeKuti v. AG of Nigeria*(1985) 2 NWLR (Pt 6)211.

⁹O W Igwe (2002) *Preliminary studies in Human Rights Law* (Lago; Rings and Favolit Ltd), 6

¹⁰UDHR, (n.7).

¹¹O W Igwe, The Human Rights to be Different: Context, Vulnerability, Values, Realities and Consequences. Rivers State University Port Harcourt Inaugural Lecture. Wednesday, 25th September 2024, 23.

¹²*Ibid.*

¹³Dave et al, Poverty, human rights and access to equity: Reflections from Nigeria

<<https://www.internationalscholarsjournals.com/articles/poverty-human-rights-and-access-to-equity-reflections-from-nigeria.pdf>> Accessed 6 October 2025.

The United Nations Development Programme,¹⁴ describes poverty as the inability to provide for physical subsistence to the extent of being incapable of protecting human dignity. The office of the high commissioner of human rights drafted the guidelines on human rights approach to poverty reduction in 2006.¹⁵ These guidelines include operational directives for a number of specific human rights in the context of poverty such as the right to adequate food, the right to portable water, the right to health, the right to education, the right to public transport and decent work, the right to adequate housing, the right to personal security, the right to appear in public without shame, the right to equal access to justice, political rights, freedoms, and the right to international assistance and cooperation.¹⁶

2.3 Extreme Poverty in the Context of Human Rights

Poverty is an assault on human dignity, but it can also reflect a violation of human rights when it is the direct consequence of government policy or is caused by the failure of governments to act.¹⁷ Extreme poverty is an assault on human dignity and a violation of the rights of humans.

Often times poverty is not seen as a human rights issue rather as the consequential effects of inability to create wealth based on individual or group's docility, laziness or mere economic inadequacies. According to the UNDP, "Poverty is a denial of human rights...the elimination of poverty should be addressed as a basic entitlement and a human right not merely as an act of charity".¹⁸

According to the recent report of the World Bank Group Poverty and Inequality Platform of June 2025¹⁹, extreme poverty can be defined as living on less than USD \$3.00 per day.²⁰ The present minimum wage in Nigeria is N70,000.00 (seventy thousand Nigerian Naira)²¹ which amounts to approximately N2,300.00 (Two Thousand, Three Hundred Naira) per day and by conversion²² it amounts to USD \$1.57 per day which is grossly below the global extreme poverty rate. Consequently, by the national minimum wage standard and considering the reality that many Nigerians are unemployed, some underemployed and some earning even below the standard national minimum wage, it can be deduced that majority of Nigerians are extremely poor.

3.0 Legal Framework

3.1 International, Regional and National Legal Framework on Poverty and Human Rights

3.1.1 Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) 1948:

The UDHR makes some provisions that clearly combats poverty. It provides in its Article 22 that everyone has the right to social security and is entitled to realization, through national effort and international co-operation and in accordance with the organization and resources of each State, of the economic, social and cultural rights indispensable for his dignity and the free development of his personality.²³ The UDHR provides further on the right to work, to free choice of employment, favourable conditions of work and protection from unemployment.²⁴ It further provides on right to basic elementary and compulsory education²⁵ and further in its Article 25 it provides that:

Everyone has the right to a standard of living adequate for the health and well-being of himself and of his family, including food, clothing, housing and medical care and

¹⁴UNDP 1996 <https://hdr.undp.org/content/human-development-report-1996>.

¹⁵Principles and Guidelines for a Human Rights Approach to Poverty Reduction Strategies, OHCHR 2006. <<https://www.refworld.org/policy/legalguidance/ohchr/2006/en/46987>> Accessed 13 October 2025.

¹⁶*Ibid.*

¹⁷ Human Rights Insights No. 1 Center For Economic and Social Rights <https://www.cesr.org/sites/default/files/CESR_Briefing_-_Human_Rights_and_Poverty_-_Draft_December_2009.pdf> Accessed 6 October 2025.

¹⁸UNDP. Poverty reduction and human rights: a practice note, 2003. Available at: <<http://www.undp.org/poverty/practicenotes/povertyreduction-humanrights0603.pdf>>. Last access on August 2006.

¹⁹ World Bank Poverty and Inequality Platform (PIP) <<https://pip.worldbank.org/home>> Accessed 10th October 2025.

²⁰*Ibid.*

²¹National Salaries and Wages Income Commission NSWIC <<https://nsiwc.gov.ng>> Accessed 11 October 2025.

²²NG Currency Rate Today <<https://ngn.currencyrate.today/convert/amount-2300-to-usd.html>> Accessed 11 October 2025.

²³UDHR 1948, Art 22.

²⁴*Ibid*, Art 23.

²⁵*Ibid*, Art 26.

necessary social services, and the right to security in the event of unemployment, sickness, disability, widowhood, old age or other lack of livelihood in circumstances beyond his control.²⁶

The UDHR although it is a declaration hence non-binding, and despite that expressly not using the word poverty, it established freedom from poverty as integral to dignity and human rights which forms the foundation for subsequent legally binding treaties.

3.1.2 International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR) 1966:

The ICESCR states that all peoples have the right of self-determination, by virtue of that right they freely determine their political status and freely pursue their economic, social and cultural development.²⁷

The ICESCR directly addresses the root causes and conditions of poverty through binding obligations on states to ensure basic needs and equality of opportunity. Thus, it made similar provisions as the UDHR as regards the right to work, to favourable employment, social security ectera as obligations on the state parties.²⁸

ICESCR transforms the UDHR's aspirational provisions into legally binding obligations, making the fight against poverty a core duty of states. It recognizes that eliminating poverty is necessary for the enjoyment of all economic, social, and cultural rights.

3.1.3 African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights 1981²⁹

Adopted and domesticated in Nigeria as the **African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights (Ratification and Enforcement) Act 1983**.³⁰ The Charter links poverty to the collective rights of peoples to development and a satisfactory environment. The Charter treats poverty not merely as an individual misfortune but as a structural and collective challenge requiring state action.

Several of the provisions of the Charter without outrightly using the word 'poverty' addressed the structural conditions and consequences of poverty in the African context. The Charter makes provision for right to work under favourable conditions,³¹ right to enjoy the best attainable state of physical and mental health,³² right to education³³ right to economic, social and cultural development³⁴ and all peoples shall have the right to a general satisfactory environment favourable to their development.³⁵

3.1.4 The Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended)

Chapter II³⁶ of the Nigerian Constitution titled the Fundamental Objectives and Directive principles of state policy, clearly adopted the UDHR and the ICESCR provisions on human rights as it relates to economic, social and cultural rights. The challenge with the Chapter II provision of the Nigerian Constitution is that the provisions are non-justiciable hence ineffective as no cause of action can arise from there before any court in Nigeria.

3.1.5 The National Human Rights Commission (Establishment) Act

The National Human Rights (Establishment) Commission Act³⁷ is a national legislation that established the National Human Rights Commission (NHRC) in 1995. The Act was amended in 2010. It empowers the NHRC with quasi-judicial powers to investigate rights violations, summon individuals and evidence, and award compensation to victims.

²⁶*Ibid*, Art 25.

²⁷ICESCR 1966, Art 1.

²⁸(n)27, Art 6, 7, 9, 11(1), 12.

²⁹ACHPRA 1981.

³⁰ACHPRA CAP A9, LFN 2004.

³¹ACHPR Art 15.

³²*Ibid* Art 16.

³³*Ibid* Art 17.

³⁴*Ibid* Art 22.

³⁵*Ibid* Art 24.

³⁶CFRN 1999 (as amended) Ss 13 - 24

³⁷NHRC (Amendment) Act 2010 LFN 2004 cap N46.

3.1.6 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs, 2015–2030)³⁸

The United Nations through its agency the **United Nations Development Programme (UNDP)** enforces its SDGs especially the first SDG goal on - No poverty, total poverty eradication.

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), also known as the Global Goals, were adopted by the United Nations in 2015 as a universal call to action to end poverty, protect the planet, and ensure that by 2030 all people enjoy peace and prosperity. The very first three of the 17 goals of the SDGs are No poverty, zero hunger and, good health and well-being.

3.1.7 UN Guiding Principles on Extreme Poverty and Human Rights (2012)

The UN Guiding Principles on Extreme Poverty and Human Rights, adopted by the UN Human Rights Council in 2012.

Based on international human rights norms and standards, the Guiding Principles provide for the first-time global policy guidelines focusing specifically on the human rights of people living in poverty.³⁹

3.2 Institutional Framework

3.2.1 National Human Rights Commission (NHRC),

The NHRC was established by the **National Human Rights Commission (Establishment) Act, 1995**, as amended by the **NHRC Amendment Act, 2010**. It is mandated to promote, protect, and enforce human rights in Nigeria in line with the Constitution, African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights, and international treaties to which Nigeria is a party.

The Commission serves as an extra-judicial mechanism for the respect and enjoyment of human rights. It also provides avenues for public enlightenment, research, and dialogue in order to raise awareness on Human Rights issues.⁴⁰ The Commission send annual reports and *laissez* with the UNDP in its reports.

The major limitation of this Commission is that it lacks judicial enforcement powers hence it can only recommend remedies but cannot compel their enforcements.

3.2.2 National Social Investment Programme (NSIP),⁴¹

The National Social Investment Programme (NSIP) operates under the supervision of the Federal Ministry of Humanitarian Affairs, Disaster Management and Social Development (FMHADMSD). Its core objective is to eradicate poverty in Nigeria

The Programme comprises four main components:

- i. N-Power Programme– which target is to provide skills acquisition, job training, and temporary employment for Nigerian youths,
- ii. Conditional Cash Transfer (CCT) Programme: Offers direct monthly stipends to the poor and vulnerable households.
- iii. Government Enterprise and Empowerment Programme (GEEP) with the aim of providing microcredit facilities to small and medium enterprises (SMEs), market women, traders, artisans, and farmers through schemes like 'TraderMoni' and 'MarketMoni'.
- iv. National Home-Grown School Feeding Programme (NHGSFP): Aims to improve child nutrition and school enrollment by providing free, locally sourced meals to public primary school pupils, while supporting local food vendors and farmers.

The NSIP is a rights-based approach to development, reflecting Nigeria's obligations under the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR) and the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights. Its objective is to improve access to food, education, and livelihood support, advance economic, social, and cultural rights including the right to an adequate standard of living, education, and development. However, several implementation challenges undermine the program's capacity to sustainably reduce poverty and fulfil Nigeria's human rights obligations toward vulnerable populations majorly inadequate monitoring, political influence and weak institutional coordination.

³⁸SDG <https://sdgs.un.org/goals> Accessed 10 October 2025.

³⁹A/HRC/21/39 UNGPEPHR 2012 <<https://docs.un.org>> Accessed 10 October 2025.

⁴⁰NHRC <<https://www.nigeriarights.gov.ng>> Accessed 10 October 2025.

⁴¹NSIP <<https://n-sip.gov.ng>> Accessed 10 October 2025.

3.2.3 African Commission on Human and Peoples Rights

African Commission on Human and Peoples Rights is a creation of the African Charter on Human and Peoples Rights with its major purpose being the enforcement of the Charter. The Commission sees poverty as a cause and consequence of violations of human rights based on the failure of states in fulfilling the demands of the African Charter.

The Commission in its Resolution on Poverty and Human Rights in Africa 2013⁴² stated that poverty is one of the major challenges of enjoyment of human rights in Africa and urged states to see eradication of poverty as a legal duty and not just a policy option.

Two landmark cases of the Commission *Social and Economic Rights Action Center (SERAC) and Another v. Nigeria (2001)*,⁴³ here the Commission held Nigeria responsible for violating the rights to health, housing, environment, and development of the Ogoni people due to environmental degradation and neglect. Another landmark decision of this Commission is in *Endorois Welfare Council v. Kenya (2010)*⁴⁴ where the Commission held Kenya liable for violating the rights to property, development, culture, and religion of the Endorois people by evicting them.

These cases show the Commission's practical application of the view that poverty linked to state action or neglect can constitute a breach of Charter obligations.

3.2.4 United Nations Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights

The Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (CESCR) established in 1985 is a United Nations body of 18 independent experts that monitors countries' implementation of the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR) which came into force in 1976. It reviews state reports, offers recommendations for improvements, develops international standards through 'General Comments,' and examines individual complaints under the Optional Protocol to the ICESCR.⁴⁵

3.2.5 United Nations Development Programme (UNDP)

The United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) is the UN's global development network, established in 1965 by the merger of the Expanded Programme of Technical Assistance (EPTA) and the Special Fund. It operates in about 170 countries and territories, providing policy advice, technical assistance, and capacity development to promote sustainable human development.

The UNDP's overarching mission is to eradicate poverty, reduce inequalities, and build resilience in nations so they can sustain human progress. Its work is guided by the principles of human rights, equality, participation, and sustainability, all central to the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).⁴⁶

3.3 Nigerian State's Obligations and Minimum Core Obligations in Human Rights Law

State obligations entail the obligation to respect, to protect and to fulfil those human rights obligations including economic, social, and cultural rights such as the right to food, housing, health, education, and an adequate standard of living. ICESCR allows for progressive realization based on each state's maximum available resources⁴⁷ however despite this progressive realization, states have minimum core obligations also.

The minimum core obligations as developed by the UN Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights are basic rights that must be guaranteed. They are non-negotiable baselines that must be protected by the states such as right to food,⁴⁸ right to education,⁴⁹ right to good health,⁵⁰ right to housing,⁵¹ to water

⁴² ACHPR/Res.236 (LIII) 2013.

⁴³ (2001) ACHPR 60 Commission 155/96.

⁴⁴ *Centre for Minority Rights Development (Kenya) and Minority Rights Group International on behalf of Endorois Welfare Council v. Kenya* (ACHPR) in 2010, Communication 276/2003.

⁴⁵ ECOSOC <https://ecosoc.un.org/en/events/2025/committee-economic-social-and-cultural-rights> Accessed 6 October 2025.

⁴⁶ UNDP <<https://www.undp.org>> Accessed 6 October 2025.

⁴⁷ ICESCR Art 2(1).

⁴⁸ *Ibid* Art 11.

⁴⁹ *Ibid* Art 13.

⁵⁰ *Ibid* Art 12.

⁵¹ *Ibid* Art 11.

and social security. According to the UN Guiding Principles on Extreme Poverty and Human Rights (2012),⁵² extreme poverty is a violation of minimum core obligations, as it denies access to basic rights. The African Commission⁵³ has also held that states must immediately ensure minimum essential levels of socio-economic rights and protect vulnerable communities from violations by state and private actors. Nigeria having ratified the ICESCR and codified its provisions in the Constitution and having ratified the African Charter as the African Charter on Human and People's Rights Act, Nigeria has thus accepted the legal obligations to ensure that people within its jurisdiction can enjoy rights guaranteed by these treaties. Nigeria equally has the obligation to ensure the eradication of poverty by meeting up to the minimum core obligations failure of which amounts to violations of human rights.

4.0 Extreme Poverty in Nigeria: Realities, Causes and Human Rights Implications

According to the Nigeria Multidimensional Poverty Index MPI 2022, 63 percent of Nigeria's population which was about 133 million persons are multidimensionally poor experiencing deprivations in health, education and living standards. The report stated that poor people in Nigeria experience over one fourth of general deprivation; the Nigeria MPI shows that poor people in Nigeria experience just over one quarter of all possible deprivations.⁵⁴

The present minimum wage in Nigeria is N70,000.00 (seventy thousand Nigerian Naira)⁵⁵ which amounts to approximately N2,300.00 (Two Thousand, Three Hundred Naira) per day and by conversion⁵⁶ it amounts to USD \$1.57 per day. World Bank Group Poverty and Inequality Platform in June 2025,⁵⁷ defined extreme poverty as living on less than USD \$3.00 per day.⁵⁸

Considering that most Nigerians, however, are not affected by changes in the minimum wage, because majority of the working age employed population work in the informal sector, mostly as farmers, traders or providers of services,⁵⁹ it therefore implies that Nigerians are majorly living under extreme poverty. The present living conditions in Nigeria is marked by a high poverty rates and an increasing cost of living crisis as a result of high inflation, unemployment and general economic hardship. Food insecurity is a major challenge also, housing deficit, high poverty and inequality. These economic hardship, poverty, high cost of living and unemployment in Nigeria are the antecedents of insecurity and high level of criminality presently experienced in Nigeria as many youths are either unemployed or under employed thus exposed to various kinds of vulnerabilities. This high poverty rate in Nigeria is caused by inequality, unemployment, corruption, government failure to protect the economic, social and political rights of the people.

Poverty is both the cause and consequence of violations of human rights. Poverty translates into structural denial of life when people cannot afford food, water, or medical treatment effectively amounting to an indirect violation of the right to life. Poverty leads to avoidable deaths through hunger, malnutrition, lack of medical care, unsafe water, environmental hazards, and violence. The UN Guiding Principles on Extreme Poverty and Human Rights (2012)⁶⁰ affirms that "People living in poverty experience interrelated deprivations that prevent them from realizing their civil, cultural, economic, political and social rights."

The UN Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (CESCR) stresses that failure to ensure access to essential primary healthcare breaches a minimum core obligation under Article 12 of the ICESCR. When the state fails to provide the minimum essential resources to sustain life, it breaches its

⁵²HRC Resolution 21/11 of 27 September 2012.

⁵³*SERAC v. Nigeria, Communication* 155/96.

⁵⁴ NG MPI 2022 <https://www.nigerianstat.gov.ng/pdfuploads/NIGERIAMULTIDIMENSIONAL_POVERTY_INDEX_SURVEYRESULTS2022.pdf> Accessed 6 October 2025.

⁵⁵National Salaries and Wages Income Commission NSWIC <<https://nsiwc.gov.ng>> Accessed 6 October 2025.

⁵⁶NG Currency Rate Today <<https://ngn.currencyrate.today/convert/amount-2300-to-usd.html>> Accessed 10 October 2025.

⁵⁷ World Bank Poverty and Inequality Platform (PIP) <<https://pip.worldbank.org/home>> Accessed 10th October 2025.

⁵⁸(n)19.

⁵⁹National Bureau of Statistics's Nigeria Labour Force Survey Report Q2 Report released on November 2024, the proportion of persons in self-employment in Q2 2024 was 85.6%. NBS NLFS Q2 2024

<https://www.nigerianstat.gov.ng/pdfuploads/NLFS_Q2_2024.pdf> Accessed 6 October 2025.

⁶⁰UNGPEPHR (n)36.

positive obligation to protect the right to life. Poverty and ill-health are mutually reinforcing disease that causes loss of income, and lack of income denies access to treatment, creating a vicious cycle of right-to-health violations. Poverty restricts access to health facilities, nutritious food, and safe environments. The poor are more exposed to environmental pollution, unsafe housing, poor sanitation, and inadequate healthcare.

In Nigeria, high poverty correlates with child mortality, maternal deaths, and deaths from preventable diseases like malaria or cholera. Example the Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey⁶¹ shows that infant and under-five mortality rates are significantly higher among poor households.

Education is both a human right and a tool for escaping poverty; when poverty denies education, it locks people out of future rights realization. Poverty strips individuals of dignity by denying them control over their lives, thereby violating the core value underlying all human rights. Widespread poverty means that development is not people-centered; it becomes elitist, violating the right to development and entrenching inequality.

The Nigeria Multidimensional Poverty Index MPI 2022⁶² statistics shows that 29% of all school-aged children are not attending school, 94% of all out-of-school children are poor. Thus 27% of all school-aged children are both poor and out of school.

Each of these rights is interconnected. Poverty triggers a cascade of violations. There is an interconnectivity between loss of income, lack of housing, denial of education and hunger, exposure to sickness and perpetuation of inequality. This deprivation demonstrates why the UN and African human rights systems treat poverty eradication as both amoral imperative and a legal duty.

5.0 Enforcement Challenges and Gaps

The Nigerian Government has not acted adequately to meet up to its legal and moral obligation of protecting the rights and dignity of its people in ensuring the eradication of extreme poverty. Majority of Nigerian youths are either unemployed or underemployed, the employed persons are grossly underpaid as the national minimum wage is not even a guarantee of an exit from poverty. The National Social Investment Programme (NSIP),⁶³ set up by the past administration in Nigeria to help curb poverty in line with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals⁶⁴ is ineffective as a result of poor implementation and corruption. The Nigerian state is presently unproductive hence do not have resources to generate income consequently is incapable of providing employments. The consequential effect of these deprivations is the increase in different kinds of crimes such as robbery and internet crimes/cybercrimes, insecurity challenges etcetera.

The vulnerable groups are not left out especially, the physically challenged, children and the elderly. Nigeria MPI recently showed that 94% of all out-of-school children are poor,⁶⁵ infant and under-five mortality rates are significantly higher among poor households.⁶⁶

Non-justiciability of socio-economic rights is the most fundamental obstacle to the enforcement of socio-economic rights under many national constitutions, including Nigeria. The 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (as amended) places socio-economic rights—such as the right to education, health, housing, and social welfare—under Chapter II: Fundamental Objectives and Directive Principles of State Policy.⁶⁷ Section 6(6)(c)⁶⁸ expressly ousts the jurisdiction of the courts from adjudicating matters contained in Chapter II, rendering these rights aspirational rather than enforceable.

This constitutional arrangement creates a stark divide between civil and political rights, which are enforceable under Chapter IV, and economic, social and cultural rights, which are treated as policy goals.

⁶¹NDHS 2023-2024 <<https://dhsprogram.com/pubs/pdf/PR157/PR157.pdf>> Accessed 13 October, 2025.

⁶²MPI (n)54.

⁶³NSIP (n)41.

⁶⁴SDG (n)38.

⁶⁵MPI(n)54.

⁶⁶*Ibid.*

⁶⁷CFRN 1999 (as amended) Chap. II.

⁶⁸*Ibid.*

Consequently, individuals deprived of basic necessities of life cannot directly invoke judicial protection. The courts have often reinforced this barrier, holding that Chapter II provisions are non-justiciable unless transformed into enforceable law through legislation.

However, the African Charter, domesticated in Nigeria through the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights (Ratification and Enforcement) Act⁶⁹ provides an alternative pathway. The Charter recognizes socio-economic rights including the right to health, education, work, and development as justiciable. The Nigerian Supreme Court in *Abacha v Fawehinmi*⁷⁰ affirmed that the Charter, being part of domestic law, supersedes inconsistent national legislation. Despite this, practical enforcement through the courts remains limited because of judicial conservatism and lack of awareness among litigants and lawyers.

Poor Accountability and Remedies, Weak institutional and policy frameworks. Limited judicial activism.

Accountability mechanisms are essential to translate rights from paper to practice. In Nigeria, enforcement suffers from a pervasive culture of impunity and weak remedies. Administrative corruption, poor transparency, and lack of oversight in public spending mean that resources meant for poverty alleviation often fail to reach intended beneficiaries.

Moreover, access to justice remains limited by poverty itself. The high cost of litigation, delays in the judicial process, and lack of legal aid prevent vulnerable groups from pursuing remedies. Although the Legal Aid Council Act and NHRC provide some assistance, their reach is minimal relative to Nigeria's population of over 200 million. The absence of collective redress mechanisms such as class actions for socio-economic rights further weakens accountability.

Towards a Rights-Based Framework for Addressing Extreme Poverty in Nigeria

Extreme poverty in Nigeria remains both a developmental and human rights crisis. Despite abundant natural resources and successive poverty-reduction programmes, millions of Nigerians continue to live in deprivation, lacking access to food, housing, healthcare, education, and dignified livelihoods. This persistence underscores the failure of conventional, charity-oriented approaches that treat poverty as a social problem rather than a rights violation.

6.0 CONCLUSION

This paper has examined extreme poverty through the lens of human rights, arguing that it transcends mere economic deprivation to constitute a fundamental violation of human dignity and internationally recognized rights. The analysis underscores that addressing poverty requires more than welfare interventions; it demands legal recognition and enforceable socio-economic rights. In the Nigerian context, this calls for constitutional and institutional reforms that make socio-economic rights justiciable and integrate rights-based approaches into national development policies. A transformative framework anchored on accountability, participation and equality is essential to break the persistent cycle of poverty. Future research should explore practical mechanisms for implementing such a rights-based framework, including the role of the judiciary, civil society, and international cooperation in enforcing the right to an adequate standard of living for all Nigerians.

In conclusion extreme poverty in Nigeria can be clearly observed as the direct consequence of government policies or failure of government to act. With the present economic reality being experienced by majority of people living in Nigeria especially the youths, the possibility of a revolution might be imminent.

7.0 RECOMMENDATIONS

1. An amendment to Nigerian Constitution to make socio-economic rights justiciable: Nigerian legislatures should amend the present constitution to elevate socio-economic rights; the rights to education, health, housing, and social welfare from non-justiciable principles under

⁶⁹Cap A9, LFN 2004.

⁷⁰(2000) 6 NWLR (Pt. 660) 228.

Chapter II to enforceable rights. This would ensure greater accountability from the state, provide citizens with a legal basis to seek redress for violations and align with the provisions of the ICESCR and the African Charter on Human and People's Rights.

2. Poverty reduction strategies and social investment programmes should be grounded in human rights principles, including participation, accountability, equality, and non-discrimination. Integrating these principles into policy design and implementation will ensure that anti-poverty measures respect human dignity, promote social justice and thus right based approaches will be incorporated in the Policies:
3. There is need to strengthen institutions and judicial enforcement. Strengthening institutions such as the National Human Rights Commission (NHRC) and the judiciary is essential to the effective protection of socio-economic rights. The availability of adequate funding, capacity building and institutional independence will enable these bodies to monitor compliance, adjudicate rights violations and advance a rights-based approach that will enhance the eradication of extreme poverty in Nigeria.
4. Improve in Nigerian Economic laws, local productions need to be increased, this will improve employment and consequently reduce poverty, criminal activities, insecurity and other related social vices.

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